

CLUSTERING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION - CHIRCHIK EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. In the scientific thesis, the Department of Special Pedagogy of the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region focused on measures to ensure its effective operation through the clustering of inclusive education at the city level.

Keywords: inclusive education, special pedagogy, educational cluster, home education, “Open-Air School”, curriculum, project

Renewing Uzbekistan, like all other spheres, is increasing the challenges faced by the education sector. The new requirements of the time began to be felt, especially in the case of education. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev noted, in order to strengthen confidence in the future of Uzbekistan, to be worthy of the ancestors, reforms must begin with science, because without science there will be no results in any field. One of the most important tasks of the main reforms in the field of school education today is to prepare students to receive quality education, to choose careers in accordance with the needs of society. No matter how old this problem is, the training of competitive personnel in Uzbekistan will remain a key factor in the socio-economic development of society and the individual, and its relevance will not decrease. Indeed, if we analyze the development of developed countries, we can see that the reforms aimed at enhancing the image of society in them began primarily with the education system, including education and upbringing in kindergartens, schools, universities.

Over the past three years, large-scale work has been carried out to effectively address the problems in this area, to radically improve the system of teacher training in our country, including in the Tashkent region. Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region was established to improve the quality of education in the region, to provide teaching staff and increase scientific capacity. The institute put forward the idea of introducing the cluster method in the field of pedagogy, which has a positive impact on the development of all areas. The cluster system, effectively introduced in the education system of Tashkent region, serves to deepen the integration of science, education and industry and for the introduction of new innovative approaches. The best way to meet the needs of pedagogical staff in the region, to solve the problem of continuity, continuity and consistency between types of education is to create a regional education cluster. Currently, the Center for Pedagogical Education Cluster in Tashkent region in cooperation with higher, professional, secondary special, general secondary, preschool educational institutions, research institutes in order to train teachers, guide students in choosing the right profession, increase the activity of students based on the combination of theory and practice established. Within the framework of the center, “school-laboratories” have been established in all types of education in the region, and a number of projects are being implemented in them. The Department of Defectology of the Faculty of Pedagogy of Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute is also carrying out large-scale scientific and practical projects to organize and further improve the activities of educational clusters in

preschool and secondary schools in the region. Despite the fact that the Department of Defectology is one of the youngest departments, it is doing significant work within the cluster of pedagogical education. The department has signed cooperation agreements with Chirchik Department of Public Education, School No. 9, 23, Multidisciplinary Specialized Preschool No. 30 and Tashkent Special Boarding School for Deaf Children No. 101, Boarding School for Deaf Children No. 106. and “Laboratories” are established in these institutions.

One of the special activities of the department within the cluster is cooperation with “Zamin”, “UNICEF” and the Republican Diagnostic Center in the practical project “Introduction of Inclusive Education in Uzbekistan”. The theme of the project is “Technologies to increase the effectiveness of inclusive and home education on the basis of voluntary social and methodological efforts of students”. The head of the project, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, leading specialist in the field of deaf pedagogy F.U. Kadirova acknowledges that the education cluster is the most effective mechanism for achieving the goals and objectives of this project. For the first time in Uzbekistan, the department is actively involved in the implementation of the cluster model in inclusive education.

It is known that the success of the pedagogical education cluster is achieved through the introduction of projects with clear mechanisms in this area and increasing the volume of research in this area. F. Kadirova has been working hard in this direction at the institute. Under the scientific guidance of F. Kadirova about 20 scientific researches on introduction and improvement of the cluster in inclusive education are carried out. Today a number of professors, masters, bachelors of the institute students have also begun research in this area. The projects implemented by the team of the Department of Defectology in the implementation of educational policy through the scientific substantiation of cluster training systems and cluster mechanisms for the purpose of methodologically, organizationally, pedagogically and psychologically correct organization of the activities of teachers, parents, partner organizations in inclusive and correctional education, serves to ensure the beneficial participation of the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute. F.U. Kadirova who managed to popularize the educational cluster at international conferences, has briefed the international scientific community on the importance and effectiveness of the cluster model introduced in Uzbekistan in the system of inclusive education at an international conference in Russia.

The staff of the department conducts research on the introduction of new projects in education and the dissemination of its results. The department implemented the project "Improving the methodology of comprehensive preparation of children with disabilities for inclusive and specialized school education in the context of the education cluster" to implement the process of preparing children with disabilities for inclusive and specialized school education in Chirchik № 30 Preschool. At the same time, methods of effective preparation of children with disabilities for inclusive and specialized school education will be improved based on the requirements of the state program “First Step” and the study, analysis and optimization of the content of the pedagogical process. Mechanisms for organizing innovative activities of teachers of preschool education organizations within the project are educational, methodological, medical, personal development, employment for children with disabilities in higher education, regional education departments, children's creative centers, non-governmental and non-profit organizations, medical associations, neighborhood councils.

and intensive modernization of goals and objectives from other social influences on the basis of harmonization with the content of theoretical, practical training, pedagogical practice.

The project also includes an “Open-Air School” with the participation of volunteer teachers and students to compile a list of preschool children not covered by education in the community, to identify responsibilities for them with the involvement of community officials, a plan of activities under the sky and Practical work is underway to establish the dislocation. The school has further expanded its activities from 2021. In cooperation with the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region and the Chirchik city administration, the “Open School” is being implemented. In this process, in the practical-educational event “School under the open sky” in various areas, including fun games with 3-4 year olds, developmental exercises with 6-7 year olds, various methodical exercises with children with speech and hearing impairments, parents interviews with psychologists and a number of other trainings.

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Volunteers consisting of talented students are also involved in projects of practical importance related to the pedagogical education cluster of the department. The activities of projects at the department are a great help to teachers, students and cluster subjects in the field of defectology in self-development, the project provides a wide range of quality services.

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